

The Influence of Online Studies and Information using Learning Analytics

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Abstract

This research will help people with inadequate knowledge to get a better understanding of online study or e-learning. Through this study, the social impact of online users or learners can be increased, and the users can have a clear idea of online study. In this research, the graphs will be presented according to country, gender, age, online resources, etc. showing the impact of online study and information on online users. The learners will get an understandable knowledge of the type of sources, what is their purpose, and resources people can use in online study. From this, the learners will get a guide or path that how easily they can learn online for study in a more flexible way. The outcomes are visualized using the R language and Tableau with pre-processed data.

Keywords: *Online studies, analysis, investigation, techniques, comparison, and visualization.*

1. Introduction

Learning Analytics (LA) is a multi-disciplinary area concerning online studies, synthetic intelligence, information retrieval, statistics, and visualization. LA is also an area where various related study areas of Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) converge. These encompass academic analytics, action research, educational statistics mining, recommender systems, and personalized adaptive studying. LA is primarily based on four dimensions, particularly statistics and environments, i.e., information, stakeholders, targets, and techniques [1].

Nowadays, Learning Analytics (LA) is one of the main subsequences in the educational sector. The online study took a large portion of it. It has interested to work in online studies related to LA. Until now, there are many books, journals, and articles about LA. It is a new sector where

the readers can see online users in different sectors have been introduced.

The goal of this paper is to develop a new strategy for online study. This research shows the most used learning resources and the learning tools, such as traditional classroom-based systems or Massive Open Online Courses (Moocs) [2]. So, educational institutions can design the lectures online for their targeted students. So studying this research, anyone, specifically students, can be motivated by the online learning system. For example, in online learning, getting detailed information is easier. Online learning has an option to see the videos or tutorials, which is often very helpful & better for the project. Here, the percentages of online education of males or females can also be shown by visualizations. With the help of this research study, institutions such as universities, schools, and colleges can improve their study system. The teacher or professor can motivate students to change the study system to see other study purposes or gender-wise study purposes. The university also can design the lecture types for targeted students.

To achieve the objective of this research, the following process, such as monitoring, prediction, adaptation, personalization, awareness, and recommendations, has been fulfilled. Online studies help users more to come closer to practical studies.

Moreover, students get more engaged in their studies and help them achieve a good result. By reading this research, user or student will adapt to online study more frequently. Because they will inherit knowledge from this research that what type of resource people use so that they will get a

path. It will also improve future awareness of online studies. It will help learners how they can efficiently study online, and it is also used to recommend the learning source [3].

In this research, the participants' answers have been recorded face to face or via social media, web, and e-mail. Here, the target population is the user or student who uses the internet in their daily life. Alternatively, it can be said that people who have knowledge about online studies but prefer to study offline or with books. At the end of the survey, various graphs can be created by collecting all data, attributes, and scale ratings. These depend on the research requirements, the graphs that can be designed according to personal information or general information. Personal information includes age, education, profession, and others. General information includes nationality, gender, and duration of study in online studies, resources, sources, and types of studies.

2. Methodology and Implementation

2.1 Concept

In this research, an opportunity has been tried to provide for the general internet user why online studies are more flexible and secure. Moreover, it allows instructors to evaluate their teaching strategies. The development process was designed following the What-Why-How framework [4]. Here, in the paper, raw data will be collected from different sources based on studies and research. The system will visualize the following evaluation.

- Analysis of data from different sources
- Performance of users or stakeholders
- Country-wise data analysis [5].

The diagram of a simplified view of Learning Analytics (LA) is shown in figure-1,

Figure 1: General concept of LA (Modified) [3].

2.2 Learning Analytics Methods in Education

The supported open learning is a unique method of distance learning called "Supported Open Learning." Some key factors of the methodologies are as follows:

- Learning analytics analysis and process
- Data visualization tools and techniques
- Prediction
- Clustering
- Relationship mining
- Discovery with models
- Separation of data for use in the process of human judgment etc.

The implementation of the methods helps to meet the requirements of the online users as well as the teachers and the students. Such as,

- Flexible - students work where and when they want to study in order to meet their requirement, family, and other commitments.
- All-inclusive - students receive all the high-quality materials they need to learn
- Supportive - personal tutors provide academic expertise, guidance and feedback, and conduct group tutorials; and faculty advisors are available for other aspects of study
- Social - students meet through tutorials, online conferences, study networks, and course forums.

The paper's analysis provided a comprehensive overview of the analytic learning methods, benefits, and challenges of using Big Data in education. Examination of these aspects revealed positive contributions [5, 6].

In this research, the indicators used in the graphs are the age, country, gender, educational degree, starting year of online study, time duration, online study goals, online study purpose, online resources, online sources, and user remark. Considering the online survey, the appropriate visualization was identified based on different graphs. The raw data has been processed by programming R. The analyses utilizing the What-Why-How framework, represented by the so-called Identifier Description Cards (IDC), are shown in figure-2 and figure-3.

Figure 2: IDC of the Vis Idiom on the Starting Year of Web Surfing Among Online Users.

Figure 3: IDC of the Vis Idiom on Online Users in Different Countries by Gender.

Therefore, this research provides a detailed description, and the implementation, and development process of the application tool. The teachers can evaluate their teaching strategy by evaluating their exam styles; analyze enrollment patterns, average grades, and students' information. Teachers can do this through the process of learning analytics. Student can also evaluate their progress through this process. However, focused on the general user's online studies aspect, the teachers' and students' aspect was not included in the initial design process. As mentioned already, mainly focused on the percentages of people who study online or who want to learn online. Then, it has focused on teachers and students. Here, the platform to provide an opportunity for teachers to evaluate their teaching strategies has extended. Students can also do their

research or contact the teachers for guidance through this process. This part of this survey is, therefore, only discussed in the result section of this paper. The research paper's core aim was to visualize online studies data country-wise in a useful way and through the online survey process. The development process consisted of three stages: Observation, Prototyping, or evaluation of the prototypes, and implementation.

Before entering the actual implementation segment, generated ideas, and layout concepts must be tested on the relevant target group. As the call to the next phase implies, prototypes must help generate comments, and ensure consumer acceptance. Besides, prototypes can be used to review exceptional concepts and designs and make good layout choices [7].

With the help of a tool named Moqups, distinct prototypes for rapid prototyping, distinct prototypes have been developed. All of which confirmed a unique color theme, included distinct attributes, one-of-a-kind indicators, and few changes in functionality, even as always consistent with the recognized center functionalities, are developed. It is because of the education, age differences of online users, and online users' chances in Asia compared to Europe, the US, or other countries.

2.2 Tools and Technologies

As we can see, data has been managed to distinguish between logic, views, and especially the styling in this research. Functions that need to be shared across multiple pages are exported to R programming files. The browser's local storage and query parameters were used for passing variables (e.g., filters, attributes, indicators, study online) between pages. The data is stored, and loaded from a CSV file, displaying only from the survey's collected data.

3. Survey Process and Analysis

Generally, the survey data are collected from the questions from person to person. The survey types have been chosen by the requirement of the research.

In every survey, there is a theory according to the research. In that case, the concept should be reliable, and transparent. The measure of the survey depends on the questionnaires and the population of the survey. The more the participant, the accurate result can be achieved. After that, the statistical result of the data has been obtained. Here, the content of the questionnaires, and the scope of the survey depend on the research. There can also be time boundaries. There are other terms, reliability, and validity of the data, which depend on the research, and the survey types [8].

Finally, the response of the end-user refers to the comments of the participants. The answer to this is the data that completes all other responses. They show that online education is more effective than traditional learning or not. After obtaining all the data, it has been analyzed and visualized by programming language R, and Tableau software.

3.1 What-Why-How Framework

Acquainting the most useful visualization language for a particular use case is a challenge. Some researchers argue that "The vast majority of possibilities within the design space will be ineffective for a unique context of use" and therefore proposes a three-part analysis named the What-Why-How framework, which represents answers to the corresponding data task idiom triplet [4].

Figure 4: What-Why-How Framework (Modified) [5].

Because of the research requirements resulting from the previous survey, suitable user goals were diagnosed to determine which suitable visualizations should be found. The analysis using the What-Why-How framework can be presented using the so-called Identifier Description Card (IDC) [6].

3.2 Research Questions Analysis

There are three key components that need further clarification for higher education stakeholders to help them effectively apply learning analytics in higher education. Educators must face the task of reviewing the literature to become familiar with LA methods, benefits, and challenges. To address the problem, the following questions guided this review:

1. What techniques are available to perform learning analytics in education?
2. What are the advantages of using learning analytics in education?
3. What are the limitations of using learning analytics in education?

Further identifying and describing LA methods, benefits, and challenges can easily help educators in higher education integrate LA to improve student learning [9].

The what-why-how analysis enabled the selection of the most commonly used visualization. To understand the Human-Centered Design (HCD) approach, the idea was presented to potential clients and the accompanying inquiries were conducted to identify goals and questions that a second degree might have regarding an emotionally supportive determination network [10]. At these points, several research questions arise and are discussed as follows:

1. What functionality would help to find specific information?
2. What are the essential attributes of online study?
3. What would be the desire for a survey useful to educational institutions?
4. What type of general information is the user looking for online?
5. Why are online surveys most popular in Europe and the USA and not in other Asian countries?
6. Why are young stars more interested in online studies than adults?
7. Why is online data more protected and secure than store massive amounts of data by documents?
8. Why is digital data easy to handle so that freelancers and clients alike can benefit from it?
9. What type of news or information are job holders or business people looking for online?
10. Why are online studies more convenient in every way these days?

The responses helped identify the core functionalities that should be given and the features of an online study that are likely to be of most interest to students, teachers, and researchers. Respondents considered the ability to compare data, a detailed overview of exciting topics among teachers and students, filtering by aspects such as exam-style, bonus points, exercises, and the ability to see data in each sector as most relevant or accessible. Online studies can reduce the problem of difficulty in finding data of any kind; the quality of data or real information can be determined very fluently as a result, and satisfaction with online studies has been identified as a key feature [11]. At the end of the discussion, further steps will show the plan to integrate

these identified core functionalities into the online studies or e-learning.

4. Visual Representation of the Findings

4.1 Results through Tableau Visualizations

In this paper, at first, the raw data has been taken from the survey, and then the raw data are analyzed. Data have been collected from indoor and outdoor surveys. Therefore the analysis part has been done with tableau software, and programming language R, and then trend data has been obtained. Thus, the graphical representation of this survey will be shown in such a way as follows;

Figure 5: Learning Goal or Learning Resource According to Age.

The above graph in Figure-5 is a Circle view. The chart is obtained by Tableau software by processing the data. This graph shows the relationship between learning goals and learning resource types. Learning resources and learning goals are shown on the x-axis. On the other h, it shows the range of age in the y-axis. Here, the survey data shows that among the age of 20 to 50 people do online surfing. For example, in this graph, students or users, at the age of 23, study for online tutorials. It also shows users most interested in online news, and blogs, online study materials, online articles, and tutorials that depend on age.

Figure 6: Online Users According to Gender, and Place of Studies.

In Figure-6, the graph is a Side by side bar chart. The Tableau software obtains the chart by processing the data like others. This graph shows the relationship between gender and place of online studies according to the highest number of records. Here, the place and gender are shown on the x-axis and the number of records is shown on the y-axis. According to this survey, the survey data shows that males mostly do online surfing more than females among the most top records. It also shows that in both cases, males and females preferred an online study place as a home.

Figure 7: Learning Resource Types by Gender.

The Pie charts are presented in Figure-7. It shows the rates of learning resource types according to males and female online users. Here it shows that both males and females are interested in videos and online study materials rather than other learning resources, but the percentage of females is a little bit more than males.

Figure 8: Learning Resources According to Different Year.

In figure-8, the graph is a Gantt chart. This graph shows the relationship between learning resources and different years of online studies among the participants according to the highest number of records. Here, learning resources are shown on the x-axis, and the years are shown on the y-axis. The survey data shows that most users believe that online studies are more effective in recent years than in the past.

4.2 Visualizations of R Functions

The different visualizations through R programming are as follows:

Figure 9: Starting Year of Web Surfing in Different Countries Online Users.

The above bar chart in Figure-9 has been obtained by processing the data in programming R. It mainly represents the internet surfing year of online users in the x-axis comparing with recent years shown in the y-axis. From the year 1990 to 1995, there are few online users, approximately two percent online users. Whereas in the year 2019, it is almost 49 percent among 50 percent. So, it can be said that from the past to recent more and more people are interested in surfing online.

Figure 10: Gender-Specific Review for the Learning Goals.

Figure-10 shows the percentages of gender review according to age shown in the x-axis for different learning objectives shown in the y-axis. Suppose the learning objective of females and males can be different according to age.

Figure 11: Daily Online Study Duration by Gender and Country.

The above Figure shows the time duration and gender in the x-axis, which shows online study hours per day according to different countries. Different countries are indicated on the y-axis. By this, anyone gets an idea of how often people study online. For example, in Bangladesh and Brazil, 40 percent of females surfing online on average daily two hours, whereas 80 percent of males daily surfing for approximately two hours.

Different visualizations have been made at the end of the survey, collecting all the data, attributes, and scale ratings. These depended on the research requirements, and charts have been prepared according to personal information or general information. Personal information includes age, education, profession, and general information, including nationality, gender, spending time in online studies, and types of research. Various online users' views have been visualized through the above graphs.

4.3 Limitations and Challenges

- Many websites require payment,
- Insufficient internet in rural areas,

- Sometimes correct or accurate information is not available in some sectors,
- In some cases, information is so massive that people are confused about what is correct or what to choose,
- Some people are not interested in web search, especially seniors.
- The review of the literature revealed the LA challenges about data tracking, collection, analysis, a connection with learning sciences and ethical concerns regarding legal and privacy issues.

Therefore, the problem is that the inclusion of LA in evaluating data in higher education diverts faculty attention from clearly identifying methods, benefits, and challenges of using LA in higher education. However, the literature review also revealed negative considerations for the use of learning analytics. For these reasons, a closer look at these aspects may lead to different findings.

5. Conclusions

The paper aimed to evolve online studies on the user-side. Theoretically, the approach was followed together with the What-Why-How analysis framework. This process has followed further work.

5.1 Outcome

The outcome of this research is a simple data survey in online studies. The usual use case would determine what information to choose as per requirements, research, or other studies.

At first, a minimalistic graph of online users will be shown. After that, the average percentages of each user group can be done by the visualization process. Other available categories are the necessity of previous knowledge, difficulty, pacing, and organization, satisfaction with the learned and overall quality.

5.2 Result Analysis

Initially, country-wise data collected through the survey were visualized. Different countries' online users' data has been obtained and visualized by various graphs. After that, it has been assumed that different data by different indicators can also be shown. Such as daily online study duration, age, country, gender, educational degree, online study goals, online study purpose, online resources, online sources, and user remark has been added for getting multipurpose readings.

Therefore, different strategies were investigated to support interactivity, and the raw data were processed by tableau and R programming. Moreover, starting a concept has been created. By this concept, a survey has been conducted to collect data. Then the raw data has been analyzed and achieved the expected graph through visualization.

In educational institutions, the professors and the teachers can overview online studies through these graph visualizations. So, that they can teach or guide their students properly. By reading this research paper, the general stakeholders or students can be influenced to study online and e-learning more. Moreover, the government of those countries where online studies are inadequate can influence and improve the online study service.

5.3 Further Work

In this research, most of the steps have been based on the online survey process, which was incorporated in the making plans and improvement techniques of these interactive web users. Nevertheless, because it is far from a theoretically primarily based research, the person degrees of the commonly iterative circle were only carried out once. Future steps would be sizable Testing by the target institution and implementing the resulting modifications of the application. Other ability modifications or debatable troubles situations are the facts and code base of the application.

However, due to resource restrictions, the individual stages of the data used in this paper are mainly bound to the online survey carried out. A continuation of the investigation could simply guarantee an extension of the dataset, but answer possibilities (e.g., agree, disagree, neutral) are firmly embedded in the code. This means that the type of data must follow a fixed structure for an extension of the application as it currently exists. However, since the survey was primarily based on the general online user evaluation forms, the integration of data generated from those forms should not require too much effort. Another data-related aspect is the effort involved in data adjustment. Although this survey allows the data to be exported to CSV, the exported dataset is not entirely in the desired CSV format to enable a smooth import using Programming R and tableau's CSV method. Also, special characters, commas, and different spellings of courses result in a fundamental revision of the exported dataset [12].

This research has shown that a web survey has many advantages instead of a paper-based evaluation bureaucracy. All users, along with students or teachers, are asked to complete the survey online, such as through an

online portal or email. This technique has a broader range of insurance than the distribution of the survey bureaucracy itself. Besides, the information should not be transferred from paper to digital. In the high-quality case, it enables direct integration into a current system. A more significant, variable, and easily expandable application would also be guaranteed using an established Internet framework. Due to the lack of individual experiences with a web framework, it was decided to use pure JavaScript and HTML. After a few tests run with unique frameworks at the beginning of the improvement phase, learning a new framework seemed to be an excessive time risk. Since the planned application seemed to be very manageable, the framework here would not be used here, which was considered the right decision. However, when reviewing the implementation and final code, it is definite that using a framework may have been a better choice. Of course, the code quality could have benefited from this. Besides, the extensibility of the application, in addition to its documentation, could be more accessible. The development of visualization without "programming guidelines" also made the collaboration very difficult. Loading times could also be extended by granting access to system-intensive variables. Given these types of problems, it can be said that future work should aim to advance the web survey as soon as possible.

5.4 Recommendations

In terms of future work, advanced interactions can be included in online education, such as people can survey in a massive way to get the exact percentages. A tool or software can be made through this process afterward in which the data of the whole world's online users' can be represented. By this, people and educational institutions will get a path to follow how they get more advantages in the online study that will be more influenced in online studies.

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